

REVIEW: *HOW FAR IS CHINESE SOCIAL SCIENCE FROM SCIENCE?*

BY QIAO XIAOCHUN

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Qiao Xiaochun 乔晓春. 2017. *Zhongguo shehuikexue li kexue haiyou duo yuan?* 中国社会科学离科学还有多远 [*How Far is Chinese Social Science from Science?*] Beijing 北京: Beijing daxue chubanshe 北京大学出版社 [Beijing University Press]. ISBN: 978-7-301-27908-3 (Paperback 55.00RMB).¹

This critical commentary on the academic realities of Chinese social sciences also offers suggestions to improve the field. Professor Qiao Xiaochun's many years of experience in academic circles, both in and outside China, add authority to his timely views on the Chinese social science community. Currently, a professor and Ph.D. supervisor at the Institute of Population Research, Beijing University, Qiao focuses on population-related studies such as demographic analysis techniques, quantitative sociology, sampling surveys, census methods, and aging issues.² His presentations at Beijing University on the peculiar situation of Chinese social sciences use information presented in this book.³

Chapter One of ten chapters begins by asking questions to understand better Chinese social sciences: Why do Chinese social sciences lack the position of *yuanshi* 'academician'? Why are social scientists generally belittled? Why have untrained social scientists become "experts"? Why are social sciences and the humanities combined in the same field? Why is it relatively easy to conduct research and publish in the field of social sciences? Qiao addresses each question within the context of Chinese history and socio-political impacts on contemporary Chinese social science, demonstrating the field's lack of scientific approaches. To address the absence of the *yuanshi* position, Qiao reviews its history, noting that changes in the academic system resulted in this position being the sole province of the natural sciences. Qiao claims that ordinary Chinese believe in only one type of "scientist" - those developing trains, airplanes, and advanced technologies. In contrast, the image of social scientists has deteriorated over the years as the result of some "experts" in social sciences appearing on TV shows and spreading false information.

Chapter Two deals with definitions and examples of science and social science and the characteristics of science to illustrate pseudoscience and non-scientific approaches. This chapter provides clarity and supports the idea that social science is also "science" and may change biased views of the field in bringing more recognition to the scientific aspects of social science.

Chapter Three focuses on the peculiar characteristics of Chinese social science with Qiao using his personal experiences in studying population theories and attending academic conferences in China. Before his master's degree program, Qiao understood population study theories but grew confused in MA courses because of philosophical speculation and a lack of evidence-based concepts.

Professor Qiao shares his experience as one of the few male participants in the "International Forum for the Status of Minority Women" in Beijing. When a minority woman cited the limited number of minority female *ganbu* 'officials' as evidence of the low status of minority women, Qiao disagreed, using the concept of equality versus equity. He was disturbed by the emotional reaction of

* Lugyal Bum (Klu rgyal 'bum, Lijiaben). 2021. Review: *HOW FAR IS CHINESE SOCIAL SCIENCE FROM SCIENCE?* by Qiao Xiaochun. *Asian Highlands Perspectives* 60:436-438.

¹ Amazon price = 33USD (<https://amzn.to/3aHgPev>, accessed 20 April 2021).

² See <https://ipr.pku.edu.cn/jsdw/zzjs/233811.htm> (accessed 22 April 2021) for more information about the author.

³ For more on Qiao's presentation at Beijing University, see <https://bit.ly/3eL81oK> (accessed 22 April 2021).

female participants. Another experience was attending an academic conference for the aged, with most participants being older adults. As he describes it, the meeting was not an academic gathering but a meeting of complaints from attendees of having contributed to the country their entire lives but having not gained what they deserved. In response, the director of the China National Committee on Ageing permitted Qiao to organize the next academic conference. Qiao subsequently invited a variety of scholars, pleasing the director with the results. Conferences, Qiao maintains, are often based on the notion that only experienced people are entitled to discuss the issues. Moreover, Qiao emphasizes the lack of literature review and references in academic articles, suggesting that conclusions in Chinese social science are often based on assumptions and not evidence.

Chapter Four explains how the articles mentioned in Chapter Three fail to present actual social problems, which impact government policy, academic development, international communication, and developing premier global universities. Such a faulty academic environment hampers Chinese social science and damages Chinese society via erroneous policies and their implementation. An example of an increasingly unbalanced gender ratio of birth in China since the 1980s is given, with Chinese scholars attributing this to the traditional Chinese view of preference for boys and then implementing policies to address the issue. However, the situation has not improved. Qiao argues that such studies require building a theoretical framework to identify possible causes and collecting relevant data. The One-Child Policy and advanced technology to determine the gender of the fetus were instrumental in an unbalanced sex ratio of newborns. Qiao also discusses the negative impact of non-scientific approaches on students and academic scholars and developing world-class universities.

In Chapter Five, Qiao compares social and natural sciences, giving the differences and similarities of both fields. He examines research challenges and why social science research may be less scientific. He argues that human beings are variable and complex, presenting quandaries that natural science research may not face. Consequently, while social science research results may seem less scientific, this does not mean social science methodology is less scientific.

Qiao elaborates on the relationships between social science and philosophy in Chapter Six, demonstrating the significant role of philosophy in the social sciences. He does this by reviewing the history of science and philosophical deduction in social science research. The highest degree title, the Ph.D., exemplifies philosophy's remarkable position. This chapter provides insights on various levels of study, such as the different objectives of learning in middle school, college, and university graduate programs. Comments on the interdisciplinary field of science and philosophy make it highly readable and noteworthy.

Chapter Seven is a guide on decision-making to avoid research failure focusing on scientific approaches illustrating the importance of such procedural and methodological flaws as irrational logic, limited samples, and erroneous data, which move conclusions in various directions. Qiao points out potential mistakes and suggests how to deal with these issues during research.

Chapter Eight is essential reading for those seeking comparisons between Chinese and American social sciences. Research methodologies, academic systems, and attitudes toward academia are drawn from his experiences in both countries. Qiao comments that overarching comparisons are nonsensical given American social science's "scientific" nature and the "speculative" nature of Chinese social science. He states that it is crucial to improve the current situation of Chinese social science.

In Chapter Nine, Qiao gives diagrams and definitions to explain various research approaches. He also suggests solutions to reinforce the development of the field, including explicitly promoting scientific research methods. Professor Qiao has organized courses on social science research methodologies during the summer holidays for young scholars and graduate students across China in practicing what he preaches.

The final chapter reminds readers that science is imperfect and the importance of recognizing the limitations of social science, given its focus on research subjects as variable as humans and human society.

Concentrated on academic aspects of Chinese social science, Qiao's uses stimulating accounts and experiences to reveal problems in the field. Organization and writing style make this book intriguing and highly readable. Those searching for a better understanding of Chinese social science and its development will benefit from reading this book, which seems particularly relevant in light of Zhou et al.'s (2009) study that notes that Chinese social science has had limited impact at the international level in the last few decades, there is considerable potential due to increased international collaboration and the many Chinese academics involved in social science.

REFERENCES

- Qiao Xiaochun 乔晓春. 2017. *Zhongguo shehuikexue li kexue haiyou duo yuan?* 中国社会科学离科学还有多远 [*How Far is Chinese Social Science from Science?*] Beijing 北京: Beijing daxue chubanshe 北京大学出版社 [Beijing University Press].
- Zhou Ping, Bart Thijs, and Wolfgang Glänzel. 2009. Is China Also Becoming a Giant in Social Sciences? *Scientometrics* 79(3):593-621.

CHINESE TERMS

ganbu 干部

Lijiaben 李加本

Qiao Xiaochun 乔晓春

yuanshi 院士